

**Differentiating Tourette Syndrome
and Functional Tic-Like Behaviors using
Spatiotemporal Keypoint Analysis**

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12-10-2025, Hildesheim

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Abstract

Machine learning methods have increasingly been applied to the study of neurodevelopmental disorders, supporting tasks such as classification and diagnosis. This project addresses the challenging problem of distinguishing between three overlapping categories: Tourette Syndrome (TS), Functional Tic-Like Behaviours (FTLBs), and patients exhibiting characteristics of both. To this end, we explored several machine learning architectures, including ensemble models, temporal convolutional networks, transformers, and graph neural networks. Each model family required tailored preprocessing, feature extraction, or transformation steps to accommodate the spatiotemporal nature of the data.

Among the implemented approaches, ensemble models and temporal convolutional networks were successfully evaluated, with XGBoost achieving the best performance, reaching a test balanced accuracy of **66%**. Furthermore, ablation studies using feature attribution methods identified key discriminative features, offering insights into clinically relevant movement patterns. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to apply these machine learning architectures to a three-class classification task involving TS, FTLBs, and their overlap—conditions that are notoriously difficult to distinguish due to shared and overlapping characteristics.

Keywords: Tourette Syndrome, Functional Tic-Like Behaviours, Neurodevelopmental Disorders, Clinical Machine Learning

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Tourette Syndrome (TS) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by involuntary, repetitive motor tics, which can range from simple actions such as eye blinking to more complex gestures. These tics fluctuate in frequency and severity over time. Functional Tic-Like Behaviors (FTLBs), on the other hand, typically have a sudden onset and tend to involve more complex and exaggerated movements. Simple behaviors like blinking, facial grimacing, and shoulder shrugging can occur in both TS and FTLB patients. However, FTLBs can often be distinguished from TS by their abrupt and later onset, limited variability over time, higher prevalence in females, and the presence of more complex motor and vocal tics. Additionally, while TS symptoms can often be voluntarily suppressed for short periods, FTLBs are typically difficult or impossible to suppress [Johnson et al., 2023, Berg et al., 2022]. Some patients with pre-existing TS may develop co-occurring FTLBs, and there are cases where individuals exhibit characteristics of both disorders [Berg et al., 2022, Cavanna et al., 2025].

The treatments for TS and FTLBs differ significantly, requiring distinct clinical approaches. Therefore, accurate differentiation is crucial to ensure appropriate treatment, reduce healthcare costs, and enable early and effective diagnosis. However, distinguishing between them remains clinically challenging due to overlapping features and the lack of objective diagnostic markers. Traditional diagnosis is based on clinical history and observation, which can be subjective and inconsistent [Brügge et al., 2023, Johnson et al., 2023, Berg et al., 2022, Cavanna et al., 2025].

This project seeks to address these challenges by applying spatiotemporal keypoint analysis—a machine learning approach using body and facial data extracted from video datasets—to develop an objective method for distinguishing not only between TS and FTLBs but also for identifying cases where both conditions co-exist. By analyzing the temporal patterns and

spatial coordination of tics, this research aims not only to apply machine learning models that outperform random baseline but also to reveal distinctive biomechanical signatures of each condition. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to apply a keypoint-based machine learning approach to video data of patients with TS, FTLBs, or both.

Section 1.1 describes existing approaches including the approaches for different disorders. Sections 1.2 present the research problem and questions guiding this project. Finally, the contributions of this research will be summarized, along with a link to the open-source code repository.

1.1 Approaches

The field of automated tic detection, particularly for distinguishing between Tourette Syndrome (TS) and related conditions, remains underexplored. As illustrated in Figure 1.1, there is a significant research focus on disorders such as Parkinson’s Disease (PD) and gait abnormalities, whereas tic detection has received limited attention [Tang et al., 2024].

To date, only a few studies have addressed tic detection directly using computational methods. One of the earlier efforts applied unsupervised learning on low-quality video data, while a more recent study introduced two approaches using high-resolution videos: one based on Random Forests and another using deep learning. Both works aim to differentiate between TS patients and healthy controls [Brügge et al., 2023, Wu et al., 2021]. However, our work targets a more challenging and less-explored classification task—differentiating between three groups: TS, FTLBs, and patients exhibiting features of both. The overlapping characteristics between these conditions make this problem particularly complex and clinically relevant.

The first study, by Wu et al. [Wu et al., 2021], introduced a two-stage framework. In the first stage, a SimCLR-inspired contrastive learning model is used to extract visual features from unlabeled video data. In the second stage, these learned representations are passed to an LSTM network to classify tics. Despite using limited annotated data, the model achieved promising results, suggesting the potential of semi-supervised learning in clinical video analysis [Wu et al., 2021].

A more recent work [Brügge et al., 2023] employed two strategies for detecting tics in TS patients using high-quality video. One approach focused on facial features extracted with MediaPipe Face Mesh. From these, 170 key landmarks were selected and used to compute hand-crafted features for classification via a Random Forest model. The second approach used bounding boxes and six key facial landmarks as input to a 3D ResNet model, offering

Figure 1.1: Distribution of papers across main objectives [Tang et al., 2024].

a deep learning-based alternative [Brügge et al., 2023].

Beyond tic detection, various machine learning methods have been developed for analyzing other disorders. These include keypoint-based and raw video-based techniques. Architecturally, models range from traditional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) to more sophisticated Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) and Transformer-based architectures [Tang et al., 2024].

However, both approaches primarily focus on facial regions. In contrast, our method leverages **both facial and full-body keypoints**, capturing the broader biomechanical context of tic-like movements. This whole-body representation is crucial for distinguishing between TS, FTLBs, and patients exhibiting both characteristics—especially considering that functional tics often manifest as exaggerated or more complex movements involving multiple body parts.

In summary, while promising methods exist, they largely focus on binary classification tasks or other neurological conditions. Our work is among the

first to attempt a multi-class classification of TS, FTLBs, and mixed cases using spatiotemporal keypoint analysis.

Section 2 will describe in detail the existing methods used for tic detection and relevant approaches from other disorder assessments that could be adapted to our specific research goal.

1.2 Research Problem & Questions

As previously discussed, there is currently no research directly addressing the differentiation between TS, FTLBs, and patients exhibiting characteristics of both. Existing studies are limited in scope—they primarily focus on distinguishing TS from healthy individuals or study the other unrelated disorders. This significant research gap opens an opportunity for exploration. However, our problem is particularly challenging due to the substantial overlap in symptoms between TS and FTLBs, further complicated by the inclusion of a third class—patients who demonstrate features of both conditions.

This research problem is grounded in designing a robust preprocessing pipeline tailored to video-based clinical data. Specifically, we develop parallel processing streams: one for the raw video recordings and another for the keypoint data extracted from both the body and face using state-of-the-art models. Our goal is to construct and evaluate various machine learning and deep learning models that can effectively process these spatiotemporal keypoints and achieve strong balanced accuracy—providing potential for real-world applicability.

To enhance interpretability and practical value, we also integrate model explainability techniques. This allows us to better understand which features contribute to classification decisions and whether these align with known clinical insights. By involving medical experts in interpreting the model outputs, we aim to iteratively refine both the models and the underlying dataset.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first research project that systematically investigates the classification of TS, FTLBs, and their overlap using full-body and facial keypoint data, while also incorporating model explainability to guide clinical relevance and trust.

This study is guided by the following research questions:

1. Can the proposed models achieve a reasonable balanced accuracy and other relevant metrics, indicating potential for clinical use?

2. Are the models capable of identifying and explaining key spatiotemporal features that distinguish between TS, FTLBs, and patients exhibiting both?
3. Do the experimental setup and evaluation protocols enable fair and meaningful comparisons between the different models explored in this study, and do they provide insights for future development?

These research questions form the foundation for the model development, evaluation strategy, and interpretability analysis presented throughout this project.

1.3 Contributions

The key contributions of this study are summarized as follows:

- We proposed and explored multiple machine learning architectures for the classification of Tourette Syndrome (TS), Functional Tic-Like Behaviours (FTLBs), and patients exhibiting both characteristics. These include ensemble models, temporal convolutional networks, transformers, and graph neural networks. Among them, two families—ensemble models (Random Forest, CatBoost, XGBoost) and temporal convolutional models (chunk-based and full-length)—were fully implemented and evaluated.
- Our experiments demonstrated that the XGBoost model achieved the best performance, reaching a test balanced accuracy of **66%** and a test accuracy of **75%**. This establishes a strong baseline for the challenging three-class classification problem.
- Beyond classification performance, we conducted ablation studies using feature attribution methods to identify discriminative spatiotemporal features. These insights not only inform further model improvements but also provide clinically relevant information that may support medical practitioners in the differential diagnosis of tic-related disorders.

The complete codebase is publicly available at <https://github.com/jafarbakhshaliyev/ticnet>.

Chapter 2

Related Work

To date, only two published studies have applied machine learning specifically to Tourette Syndrome (TS). Both focus on distinguishing TS patients from healthy controls rather than addressing the broader clinical spectrum that includes Functional Tic-Like Behaviors (FTLBs) or co-occurring cases. The methods developed in these works are reviewed in Section 2.1. Beyond TS, a variety of machine learning approaches have been developed for other neurological disorders, some of which are potentially transferable to tic classification tasks. These will be discussed in Section 2.2.

2.1 Early Studies on Tourette Syndrome

The method proposed in [Wu et al., 2021] follows a two-stage framework. In the first stage, unsupervised feature learning is applied, while the second stage implements supervised classification. The authors worked with an unlabeled pool of patient videos, which motivated the development of an unsupervised method based on SimCLR-style contrastive learning. Using a ResNet encoder, they learned visual representations by maximizing similarity between different augmented views of the same video segment while contrasting them with other segments. In the second phase, the learned features were passed into an LSTM network to capture temporal movement patterns in short clips. The model was trained for both binary and multiclass classification. In their setting, binary classification referred to distinguishing TS patients from healthy ones, while multiclass classification referred to differentiating between tic types such as eye tics, mouth tics, and others [Wu et al., 2021]. The overall pipeline is illustrated in Figure 2.1.

This approach differs from our research objectives. First, the dataset in [Wu et al., 2021] consisted of unlabeled videos, whereas our dataset is

labeled and does not contain additional unlabeled samples. Second, while we also explore recurrent architectures in combination with convolutional layers, our design and objectives are different and will be discussed in Section 3. Finally, their study was limited by low video quality and an exclusive focus on facial regions, whereas our work considers both facial and full-body keypoints.

Figure 2.1: Architecture of the two-stage method proposed in [Wu et al., 2021]. Stage 1: unsupervised feature learning with contrastive learning. Stage 2: LSTM-based supervised classification.

A more recent study [Brügge et al., 2023] proposed two alternative approaches for differentiating TS patients from healthy controls. The first was a landmark-based method, referred to as the Random Forest approach. In this method, 468 facial landmarks per frame were extracted using MediaPipe Face Mesh. Out of these, 170 landmarks were manually selected in consultation with clinicians to focus on clinically relevant regions. From the selected landmarks, statistical and geometric features (e.g., means, variances, and inter-frame distances) were computed and then classified with a Random Forest model [Brügge et al., 2023].

The second method was an end-to-end deep learning approach. Facial regions were cropped from each frame using BlazeFace, and a 3D ResNet-18 was trained directly for classification. To improve robustness, six additional facial landmarks were included. The authors also employed GradCAM to provide visual explanations, highlighting which regions of the face were most important for predictions [Brügge et al., 2023]. An overview of both methods is shown in Figure 2.2.

Both approaches used 5-minute video recordings segmented into 1-second clips (30 frames). Importantly, like the earlier study, these methods focused

exclusively on facial features. In contrast, our research expands the representation space by including full-body keypoints alongside facial data, enabling a more holistic analysis of tic-like movements.

Figure 2.2: Overview of the two algorithms proposed for tic detection in [Brügge et al., 2023]. (Top) Landmark-based Random Forest approach. (Down) End-to-end 3D ResNet approach.

2.2 Studies for Other Movement Disorders

A wide variety of model architectures have been developed for the assessment of movement disorders, including Parkinson’s disease evaluation, gait disorder analysis, tremor assessment, and related tasks. While some of these models are not directly applicable to our case, many can be adapted or extended for our purposes. This section highlights important model types and cites relevant studies as references.

Among different architectures, convolutional neural network (CNN)-based models are among the most prominent. They have been widely applied to Parkinson’s disease assessment, gait analysis, bradykinesia evaluation, and related disorders. For instance, one study combined CNNs with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks to analyze segmented handwriting signal patches, as illustrated in Figure 2.3. The model first applies an LSTM block with 128 memory units to capture temporal dependencies, followed by two 1D CNN layers with activation functions and max pooling to extract local temporal features. A fully connected network then performs the final diagnosis of Parkinson’s disease from handwriting signals [Wang et al., 2024]. This work is particularly relevant to our research, as we also adopt a CNN–LSTM hybrid architecture, though in a different configuration. Other representative CNN-based studies for movement disorder assessment include [Li et al., 2020], [Lu et al., 2021], [Lu et al., 2020], [Reyes et al., 2019], [Mehta et al., 2020], [Rajnoha et al., 2018].

Figure 2.3: CNN–LSTM hybrid model for Parkinson’s disease diagnosis from handwriting signals [Wang et al., 2024].

Another widely used approach is based on Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs), which have been applied to Parkinson’s gait recognition, freezing-of-gait (FoG) detection, and cerebral palsy assessment, among other tasks. A representative example is WM–STGCN, a specialized variant of the standard ST-GCN model for gait recognition. WM–STGCN employs a weighted adjacency matrix with virtual connections and integrates Multi-Scale Temporal Convolution (MS–TCN). The architecture consists of nine GCN blocks, each composed of a spatial module (graph convolution), a temporal module (multi-scale TCN), and a residual connection. The network concludes with global average pooling and a softmax classifier for binary classification between Parkinsonian and normal gait. As input, WM–STGCN processes walking videos, extracts skeleton keypoints using OpenPose, and constructs spatiotemporal graphs where nodes represent joints and edges represent intra-skeleton and inter-frame connections [Zhang et al., 2023]. The overall architecture is shown in Figure 2.4. In contrast to this design, our work must handle both body and facial keypoints, amounting to 133 body keypoints in addition to facial features. This requires alternative, more efficient, and state-of-the-art GCN variants to be explored. Additional GCN-based studies for disease assessment can be found in [Guo et al., 2020, Guo et al., 2021, Guo et al., 2022, Hu et al., 2019, Hu et al., 2020].

Transformer-based approaches have also recently been applied to movement disorder analysis, particularly in hand movement. Although only a limited number of transformer-based studies have been published so far, these works provide inspiration for adapting transformer architectures in our own setting [Sun et al., 2024, Zhang et al., 2022].

Figure 2.4: WM-STGCN model for Parkinsonian gait recognition [Zhang et al., 2023].

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter presents the methodological framework adopted in this study. We first motivate the importance of addressing the proposed classification task and its broader impact on both the Artificial Intelligence (AI) and medical communities (Section 3.1). Next, we give the problem formulation (Section 3.2) and describe the data collection, keypoint extraction, and preprocessing pipeline (Section 3.3). Finally, we introduce the classification models and their architectural design (Section 3.4), including additional transformer- and graph-based approaches (Section 3.5) that remain as future directions.

3.1 Motivation

Tourette Syndrome (TS) and Functional Tic-Like Behaviors (FTLBs) are often difficult to distinguish, both for clinicians and computational models. These conditions share overlapping behavioral manifestations such as blinking, facial grimacing, or shoulder shrugging, while also exhibiting subtle differences in onset, variability, and complexity. Existing studies in the literature have primarily focused on differentiating TS patients from healthy controls, which is comparatively less challenging than distinguishing between TS and FTLBs [Brügge et al., 2023, Wu et al., 2021, Tang et al., 2024].

Our task introduces an additional layer of complexity by considering not only TS and FTLBs as separate classes but also patients who simultaneously exhibit characteristics of both disorders. To the best of our knowledge, this three-class classification setting has not been previously addressed.

Solving this problem has significant clinical and societal implications. Accurate and early differentiation reduces the cost of treatment, improves patient well-being, and ensures that individuals receive appropriate therapies. Furthermore, models developed in this research could potentially

be integrated into mobile health applications, thereby providing diagnostic assistance in regions with limited access to specialists or healthcare resources [Johnson et al., 2023, Cavanna et al., 2025]. Beyond classification, these models can also highlight which body parts or facial regions contribute most to predictions, offering clinicians additional insights into the biomechanical differences between TS and FTLBs.

Given its novelty and clinical relevance, this project serves as a valuable starting point for future research. It bridges the gap between AI-based video analysis and practical clinical applications, providing benefits to both communities.

3.2 Problem Formulation

Let $\mathcal{V} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^N$ denote a set of N video samples, where each video V_i contains visual information of patients exhibiting motor behaviors. From each video V_i , we extract spatiotemporal keypoint data using two pre-trained models:

- R : a body keypoint extraction function
- G : a facial keypoint extraction function

Applying these functions to a video V_i produces a coordinate-based dataset:

$$X_i = [R(V_i) \parallel G(V_i)] \in \mathbb{R}^{T_i \times K \times 2}$$

where:

- T_i is the number of frames in the i -th video
- K is the total number of keypoints
- The final dimension 2 represents (x, y) spatial coordinates
- \parallel denotes concatenation along the keypoint axis

Given the extracted keypoint sequences $\{X_i\}_{i=1}^N$, the objective is to learn a classification function:

$$f : \mathbb{R}^{T \times K \times 2} \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2\}$$

where each label corresponds to a class:

- 0: Tourette Syndrome (TS)

- 1: Functional Tic-Like Behaviors (FTLBs)
- 2: Both (TS + FTLBs)

To achieve this, multiple models are designed, including traditional machine learning classifiers and deep learning architectures. Some of these models include an intermediate feature engineering function $g(\cdot)$ before classification:

$$f(g(X_i)) \rightarrow \hat{y}_i$$

The models are trained using the Cross-Entropy Loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{CE} = - \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=0}^C y_i^{(c)} \log(\hat{y}_i^{(c)})$$

where $y_i^{(c)}$ is the one-hot encoded ground truth label and $\hat{y}_i^{(c)}$ is the predicted probability for class c .

To address class imbalance and to ensure clinical robustness, evaluation is primarily based on **balanced accuracy**:

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{TP_c}{TP_c + FN_c}$$

where TP_c and FN_c denote the number of true positives and false negatives for class c , and $C = 3$ in our case.

The key challenge lies in modeling the temporal and spatial patterns embedded within keypoint trajectories, capturing meaningful differences among the three diagnostic categories. This formulation serves as the foundation for designing, training, and evaluating models throughout the remainder of this study.

3.3 Data Processing

The dataset used in this study consists of 740 patient videos, recorded across multiple years with different cameras. On average, each video has a length of 5–7 minutes and is sampled at 30 Hz. For privacy and data security reasons, all recordings are stored in Hannover Medical School’s secure storage system¹, with computational access provided through their university cluster. Keypoint extraction was performed directly on this system using

¹<https://www.mhh.de/en/>

two state-of-the-art models: ViTPose [Xu et al., 2022] for full-body keypoints and MediaPipe Face Mesh [Kartynnik et al., 2019] for facial landmarks.

Keypoint Extraction

ViTPose employs a Vision Transformer backbone with patch embeddings and stacked transformer encoders. It incorporates two types of decoders—a classic decoder and a lightweight decoder—making it highly adaptable across datasets. In this work, we use the whole-body version of ViTPose, which extracts 133 keypoints covering the entire body, including face regions. Each keypoint is represented by its (x, y) coordinates and a confidence score [Xu et al., 2022] (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1: Overview of ViTPose architecture: (a) overall framework, (b) transformer block, (c) classic decoder, (d) simple decoder, (e) dataset-specific decoders [Xu et al., 2022].

Since facial features play a crucial role in differentiating TS and FTLBs, we also employed the MediaPipe Face Mesh model. This model is based on an end-to-end residual neural network with aggressive subsampling in the early layers, enabling efficient real-time inference. It provides 468 facial landmarks, each with (x, y, z) coordinates. In our setting, we only retain the 2D (x, y) information [Kartynnik et al., 2019].

Altogether, the combined keypoint representation consists of 601 landmarks per frame (133 from ViTPose and 468 from MediaPipe Face Mesh).

Preprocessing Pipeline

The preprocessing pipeline is summarized in Figure 3.2. Keypoint files were transferred from Hannover Medical School to the KISSKI cluster at Leibniz University², where subsequent analysis was performed. Dataset splitting was stratified by class into 80% training and 20% testing. The resulting distribution was: TS (train: 501, test: 119), FTLB (train: 41, test: 12), and Both (train: 59, test: 8).

The preprocessing pipeline involved the following steps:

- **NaN value handling:** Files with more than 33% NaN values were discarded. Otherwise, missing values were interpolated.
- **Normalization:** Face landmarks were normalized relative to the distance between eye corners, anchored at the nose keypoint. Body landmarks were normalized relative to shoulder distance, anchored at the pelvis.
- **Confidence filtering:** ViTPose keypoints were removed if 70% of their frames had a confidence score below 0.7.
- **Noise reduction:** A Savitzky–Golay filter was applied to smooth trajectories and reduce high-frequency noise.

After these steps, the dataset was cleaned, normalized, and prepared for model training.

3.4 Models

We investigated multiple architectures to address the three-class classification problem. Two main families of approaches were considered: (i) ensemble learning models with feature engineering, and (ii) deep learning models capturing spatiotemporal patterns. Due to time limitations, Transformer- and GCN-based models are discussed conceptually but not implemented in this study.

Ensemble Models with Feature Engineering

The ensemble-based approach is illustrated in Figure 3.3. The input keypoint data, $X \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times K \times 2}$, is first segmented into sliding windows of variable lengths. From each segment, we extract statistical, geometric, frequency-based, and

²<https://kisski.gwdg.de/en/>

Figure 3.2: Preprocessing pipeline for extracted keypoints. Key steps include NaN handling, normalization, confidence-based filtering, and smoothing.

biomechanical features, such as speed, acceleration, and jerk. Additionally, cross-region correlations and local/global statistics are computed.

This process yields a tabular representation, which is then used as input for ensemble models including Random Forest, XGBoost [Chen and Guestrin, 2016], and CatBoost [Prokhorenkova et al., 2019]. To address the relatively small sample size, feature selection was applied to retain the most informative 20–30 features. Importantly, these models also provide feature importance scores, allowing interpretability of which body regions most contribute to classification.

Figure 3.3: Pipeline for ensemble learning models with feature engineering. Sliding window segments are transformed into tabular features and classified using Random Forest, XGBoost, or CatBoost.

Temporal Convolutional Models

The second architecture focuses on learning spatiotemporal dependencies directly from the keypoint sequences (Figure 3.4). Two data processing strategies were tested: (i) splitting each video into 1-minute chunks to increase the number of training samples, and (ii) using entire video sequences without chunking. The chunking approach increases sample size but risks losing information for the “Both” class, where shorter segments may capture only TS or FTLB behaviors.

After flattening the input to $X \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times 2K}$, a Conv1D layer is applied to capture local dependencies and reduce dimensionality. This is followed by a Temporal Inception Block [Ismail Fawaz et al., 2020], which applies convolutional filters of multiple receptive field sizes, combined with max-pooling and residual connections. Global average pooling and fully connected layers are then used for classification.

Figure 3.4: Temporal convolutional model architecture. Conv1D layers and Inception-style blocks capture both local and long-range dependencies in keypoint sequences.

The Temporal Inception Block design is adapted from the InceptionTime architecture [Ismail Fawaz et al., 2020], shown in Figure 3.5. Multiple convolutional kernels with varying filter lengths are applied in parallel, enabling the model to capture short-, medium-, and long-term temporal dependencies. Residual connections stabilize training and facilitate gradient flow.

Figure 3.5: Inception module from Inception-Time [Ismail Fawaz et al., 2020].

3.5 Additional Architectures

In addition to the ensemble and temporal convolutional approaches described earlier, we explored several advanced architectures that could potentially be applied to our task. Due to limited time and computational resources, these models were not fully implemented or evaluated. Nevertheless, their design and prior success in related tasks suggest promising directions for future work.

Transformer Architectures

The first transformer-based model, illustrated in Figure 3.6, is inspired by PoseFormer [Zheng et al., 2021], originally designed for 3D human pose estimation. We adapted the architecture to suit our setting, which requires differentiating between TS, FTLBs, and combined cases.

In this model, separate spatial transformers are applied to body and facial keypoints. To reduce redundancy, we excluded facial keypoints already present in ViTPose and manually selected clinically relevant landmarks from the MediaPipe Face Mesh. Following patch embedding and transformer encoding, the encoded features are concatenated and augmented with positional embeddings. A [CLS] token is introduced for classification purposes. Subsequently, a temporal transformer encoder processes the concatenated sequence to capture long-range dependencies. Finally, a classifier head predicts the three diagnostic categories. While this model provides strong representational capacity, its computational cost is substantial, particularly due to the high dimensionality of the facial keypoints, and further dimensionality reduction strategies are required.

To design a more computationally efficient transformer model, we also

Figure 3.6: Adapted transformer architecture inspired by PoseFormer [Zheng et al., 2021]. Separate spatial encoders for body and face keypoints are followed by concatenation, temporal encoding, and classification.

propose the architecture illustrated in Figure 3.7. This model is inspired by RoFormer [Su et al., 2023], which introduces Rotary Position Embeddings (RoPE) to enhance positional encoding. In this simplified pipeline, Conv1D layers are first applied to extract compact local features. These features are then passed through a transformer encoder with RoPE, followed by a classification head. This design reduces computational requirements while retaining the ability to model sequential dependencies, making it a practical option for resource-constrained environments.

Figure 3.7: Lightweight transformer model inspired by RoFormer [Su et al., 2023]. Conv1D layers and RoPE-enhanced transformer encoding allow efficient modeling of temporal dynamics.

Graph Neural Networks

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) offer another compelling framework for modeling spatiotemporal dynamics of keypoint sequences. These methods treat keypoints as graph nodes and leverage both spatial and temporal connections through graph convolutions. Prior studies have successfully applied GNNs, particularly Spatial-Temporal Graph Convolutional Networks (ST-GCN) [Yan et al., 2018], to human action recognition and neurological disorder assessment.

In our proposed design (Figure 3.8), body and facial keypoints are first reduced by manual selection of clinically relevant landmarks to minimize redundancy. The graph is then constructed as follows:

- Nodes v_{ti} represent keypoint i at time t .
- Spatial edges E_S connect anatomically related keypoints (e.g., joints connected by bones).
- Temporal edges E_T connect the same keypoint across consecutive frames, capturing motion dynamics.

The resulting spatiotemporal graph is fed into GCN-based models. While ST-GCN serves as the baseline, more advanced architectures such as 2s-AGCN [Shi et al., 2019], HD-GCN [Yang et al., 2023], and BlockGCN [Zhou et al., 2024] have demonstrated superior accuracy and computational efficiency. Among these, BlockGCN appears particularly promising for our task, offering strong performance with reduced resource requirements.

Figure 3.8: Graph-based modeling of body and facial keypoints. Nodes represent keypoints over time, with blue edges denoting anatomical (spatial) connections and green edges denoting temporal continuity. Candidate models include ST-GCN, 2s-AGCN, HD-GCN, and BlockGCN.

Chapter 4

Experiments

In this chapter, we present the datasets and their characteristics (Section 4.1), describe the experimental setup and evaluation metrics (Section 4.2), and report the main results of our models (Section 4.3). Finally, we provide ablation studies that highlight the contributions of specific features (Section 4.4).

4.1 Datasets

Table 4.1 illustrates the distribution of videos across training and testing sets. Although the dataset is relatively large, it is highly imbalanced across classes. The video length varies between 2 and 10 minutes, with an average of 5–6 minutes. The quality of videos is also heterogeneous, ranging from low to high resolution. Furthermore, recording conditions vary: some videos capture the whole body, others only the upper body (hips upwards), and some focus exclusively on the face.

Due to this variability, we applied preprocessing steps such as NaN handling and low-confidence keypoint removal to improve data quality and ensure reliable model training. Another challenge is the presence of multiple individuals in some videos, where the ViTPose model occasionally captured keypoints of practitioners moving in the background. To mitigate this, we automatically dropped frames containing more than two detected persons. While object tracking would provide a more robust solution, it was beyond the scope of this work and remains an interesting direction for future research.

As mentioned previously, the dataset was collected by a medical student and securely stored at Hannover Medical School. Due to strict privacy and data protection regulations, direct video-based methods are not permissible. Instead, we adopted a keypoint-based representation to ensure anonymity

Split	TS	FTLB	Both
Train (601)	501	41	59
Test (139)	119	12	8
Total (740)	620	53	67

Table 4.1: Distribution of videos across training and testing sets. TS: Tourette Syndrome, FTLB: Functional Tic-Like Behaviors, Both: videos containing characteristics of both disorders.

while still retaining diagnostically relevant motion information. In the next section, we describe the experimental setup and evaluation metrics.

4.2 Experimental Setup

We experimented with both ensemble models and temporal convolutional models. For the ensemble models, we selected the most important 15–20 features using their base estimators and addressed class imbalance through resampling techniques and strong regularization. Each model was trained and evaluated over 5 runs, and we report mean and standard deviation of all metrics. Confusion matrices were also generated to illustrate class-specific errors. To interpret model predictions, we used SHAP [Lundberg and Lee, 2017], which will be discussed in Section 4.4.

For the temporal convolutional networks, we trained models for 20 epochs and again report mean and standard deviation of results over 5 runs. Hyperparameter tuning was limited due to time and resource constraints, which should be considered when interpreting performance.

Given the dataset imbalance, evaluation was based on three complementary metrics: accuracy, macro-averaged F1-score, and balanced accuracy. Accuracy measures the overall proportion of correctly classified samples:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\sum_{c=1}^C TP_c}{N},$$

where TP_c denotes the number of correctly classified instances in class c , and N is the total number of samples.

The macro-averaged F1-score balances precision and recall across classes:

$$\text{F1-score}_{macro} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision}_c \cdot \text{Recall}_c}{\text{Precision}_c + \text{Recall}_c},$$

with

$$\text{Precision}_c = \frac{TP_c}{TP_c + FP_c}, \quad \text{Recall}_c = \frac{TP_c}{TP_c + FN_c}.$$

Finally, to explicitly account for class imbalance, balanced accuracy is reported as the primary metric:

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{TP_c}{TP_c + FN_c},$$

where $C = 3$ in our case. This ensures equal contribution of each class regardless of prevalence.

4.3 Main Results

In this section, we present the results obtained from the different model architectures, along with their corresponding confusion matrices.

Table 4.2 reports the performance of ensemble models averaged over 5 runs. XGBoost clearly outperformed CatBoost and Random Forest across all metrics. Notably, XGBoost achieved a test balanced accuracy of 66.0%, compared to 59.5% for CatBoost and 52.3% for Random Forest. However, all models exhibit signs of overfitting, as indicated by the gap between training and test performance. Attempts to mitigate overfitting using stronger regularization had limited effect. Future work should therefore focus on improving feature quality rather than solely adjusting regularization strength.

Model	Train Balanced Accuracy	Train F1-Score	Train Accuracy	Test Balanced Accuracy	Test F1-Score	Test Accuracy
Random Forest	0.787 ± 0.005	0.812 ± 0.003	0.785 ± 0.003	0.523 ± 0.021	0.759 ± 0.004	0.709 ± 0.006
CatBoost	0.887 ± 0.021	0.818 ± 0.017	0.792 ± 0.021	0.595 ± 0.030	0.767 ± 0.023	0.718 ± 0.027
XGBoost	0.898 ± 0.003	0.831 ± 0.002	0.809 ± 0.002	0.660 ± 0.002	0.791 ± 0.004	0.747 ± 0.005

Table 4.2: Main classification results for Random Forest, CatBoost, and XGBoost. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation over 5 runs. The best results per column are highlighted in bold.

The averaged confusion matrix of XGBoost over 5 runs is shown in Figure 4.1. It reveals common misclassifications: FTLB is frequently confused with Both, and Both is often confused with FTLB. Tourette Syndrome (TS) is occasionally misclassified as Both. This pattern suggests that the “Both” category overlaps strongly with FTLB, which explains the ambiguity. The confusion between TS and FTLB is of particular clinical interest and warrants further investigation.

Next, Table 4.3 presents the results of temporal convolutional models. Based on test balanced accuracy, the full-video Inception model performed

Averaged Confusion Matrix with Standard Deviation

Figure 4.1: Averaged confusion matrix (with standard deviations) of XGBoost over 5 runs. Misclassifications are most frequent between FTLB and Both, and between TS and Both.

better than the chunk-based version (57.2% vs. 53.3%). Both models, however, suffered from overfitting, with chunk-based Inception showing stronger signs of memorization despite attempts at regularization and loss-function adjustments. The superior performance of the full-video approach is intuitive: chunking may fragment the “Both” class into segments resembling TS or FTLB alone, thereby confusing the model.

Model	Train Accuracy	Train Balanced Accuracy	Train F1-Score	Test Balanced Accuracy	Test F1-Score	Test Accuracy
Chunk-based Inception	0.839 ± 0.019	0.761 ± 0.023	0.856 ± 0.015	0.533 ± 0.031	0.758 ± 0.001	0.723 ± 0.004
Full Video Inception	0.791 ± 0.026	0.663 ± 0.082	0.809 ± 0.011	0.572 ± 0.053	0.770 ± 0.037	0.745 ± 0.061

Table 4.3: Classification results of Inception-based models. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation over 5 runs. Bold values indicate the best result per column.

Figure 4.2 shows the confusion matrix of the full-video Inception model.

Misclassifications primarily occur between FTLB and TS, while Both is also misclassified into TS. These results indicate that although temporal convolution models can capture long-term dependencies, they still struggle with separating overlapping characteristics between FTLB, TS, and Both.

Figure 4.2: Averaged confusion matrix (with standard deviations) of the full-video Inception model over 5 runs. Most errors occur between FTLB and TS, as well as Both being confused with TS.

While these results are encouraging, there is still considerable room for improvement. Addressing class imbalance more effectively, employing stronger regularization, exploring alternative loss functions, and performing a more systematic hyperparameter search are promising directions for future work. Among all models tested, ensemble methods—specifically XGBoost—achieved the most reliable results, with a test balanced accuracy of 66% and clinically interpretable misclassification patterns. Therefore, in the following section, we focus on feature attribution and diagnosis-specific insights using SHAP analysis.

4.4 Ablation Studies and Interpretability

In this section, we analyze the contribution of individual features to the classification task by employing SHAP values derived from the XGBoost model. This allows us to identify which features are most discriminative across classes and to provide clinically meaningful interpretations of model behavior. Feature importance is presented both globally (top contributing features overall) and in a class-specific manner, highlighting which movements distinguish Tourette syndrome (TS), functional tic-like behaviors (FTLB), and the mixed *Both* class.

Figure 4.3 illustrates the top 15 most influential features across all classes. Among these, 11 originate from ViTPose and 4 from MediaPipe. Notably, although ViTPose contributes the majority, most of the highly ranked features still reflect movements of the face. MediaPipe features, such as right cheek, right eyebrow, and left eyebrow dynamics, also emerge as relevant. In addition, movements of the right ring finger, left big toe, left shoulder, and left elbow are identified as important body-related discriminators. These findings suggest that while body movements provide supporting cues, facial dynamics remain the dominant discriminative signals. For clinicians, such insights help align AI-driven patterns with clinical observations, offering potential guidance in diagnostic contexts, even though no fixed set of clinical rules fully separates the conditions.

Figure 4.4 highlights the 10 most discriminative features distinguishing TS from FTLB. Most of these are facial features, while two key body-related signals (left shoulder and right ring finger movements) also contribute. In particular, left shoulder movement appears more indicative of FTLB, whereas eyebrow- and cheek-related features are more characteristic of TS. This aligns with the observation that FTLB often presents with more variable and less stereotyped body movements.

Figure 4.5 presents the 12 most discriminative features for differentiating TS from the *Both* class. The analysis shows that right eyebrow and right cheek movements are particularly associated with the *Both* class, whereas TS is more strongly linked to a combination of facial and body movement features. This suggests that while the *Both* category can overlap with TS in certain characteristics, subtle distinctions in specific facial dynamics enable partial separation.

Figure 4.3: Top 15 most important features identified by SHAP values across all classes. ViTPose contributes the majority of features, although many of them capture facial dynamics.

Figure 4.5: Discriminative features separating Tourette syndrome from the *Both* class. Eyebrow and cheek movements are key in distinguishing the *Both* class, while TS shows more diverse body- and face-related markers.

Figure 4.4: Top discriminative features distinguishing Tourette syndrome from FTLB. Facial features dominate, but specific body movements (e.g., left shoulder, right finger) also play a role.

Finally, Figure 4.6 shows the 15 most discriminative features for distinguishing *Both* from FTLB. Compared to the previous contrasts, a greater variety of features emerge here. For instance, correlations between left and right eye movements, as well as contributions from the left big toe and left shoulder, play a role in separating FTLB from *Both*. Interestingly, the majority of highly ranked features for the *Both* class still originate from facial movements, whereas FTLB shows a stronger reliance on broader body dynamics.

Figure 4.6: Most discriminative features distinguishing the *Both* class from FTLB. Facial dynamics dominate for the *Both* class, while FTLB exhibits stronger contributions from body-related features such as shoulder and toe movements.

In summary, SHAP-based interpretability reveals that facial dynamics are consistently the most discriminative features across class comparisons, while specific body movements provide secondary but meaningful signals. These results provide not only an explanation of model behavior but also potential guidance for clinicians in assessing subtle movement patterns, although they should not be interpreted as rigid diagnostic rules.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

This chapter concludes the thesis by revisiting the motivation of our project, summarizing the results, and reflecting on the outcomes in relation to the research questions. Our work is motivated by the application of machine learning models to a highly challenging classification problem with three classes that exhibit overlapping characteristics. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to investigate the distinction between Tourette Syndrome (TS), Functional Tic-Like Behaviors (FTLB), and the combined class (*Both*), which includes characteristics of both TS and FTLB. The importance of this project lies in its potential to improve diagnostic support systems, reduce treatment costs, guide clinicians toward more effective therapies, and ultimately provide better access to care, especially in settings where specialized expertise is limited.

We explored multiple machine learning architectures, ranging from ensemble methods to temporal convolutional networks, with initial investigations also planned for transformer and graph-based models. Among the ensemble approaches, XGBoost achieved the strongest results, reaching a test balanced accuracy of 66% and an overall accuracy of 75%. Notably, XGBoost not only outperformed other ensemble models but also outperformed temporal convolutional models. Within temporal approaches, the model trained on full video sequences obtained a higher test balanced accuracy (57.2%) than the chunk-based model. This result was expected, as chunking reduces temporal context: videos labeled as *Both* may display only TS-like or FTLB-like behaviors in individual chunks, whereas clinicians typically base their diagnosis on the complete temporal trajectory of a recording. The weaker performance of temporal convolutional models is largely attributable to the lack of extensive hyperparameter tuning and resource limitations, which are further discussed in Section [5.1](#).

Given that XGBoost consistently provided the best results, it was chosen

as the primary model for interpretability analyses. Using SHAP-based feature attribution, we identified the features most relevant for classification. Interestingly, most of the discriminative features originated from ViTPose and were related to facial movements, although several body-related features also played an important role. In particular, FTLB cases were often distinguished from the other classes through complex body-part movements, whereas facial dynamics were dominant in separating TS from other conditions. This pattern is consistent with clinical insights, as FTLBs frequently involve broader, less stereotyped movements compared to TS.

In summary, this project delivers promising results and identifies biomechanical markers that may support clinical decision-making. While the proposed models are not yet sufficient for clinical deployment, they highlight important pathways for improving automated diagnosis. Section [5.2](#) will discuss potential future research directions, including methodological improvements and the exploration of additional architectures.

5.1 Challenges & Limitations

Several challenges and limitations were encountered during the project, partly due to the collaboration across different universities and the restricted timeframe. Among the implemented models, the ensemble methods were the most thoroughly tuned and evaluated, which partly explains their superior performance. Temporal convolutional networks were not carefully optimized and would benefit from more systematic hyperparameter search, architectural refinements, and advanced regularization techniques. Moreover, although transformer-based and graph-based models were planned, they could not be implemented within the given timeframe and resources. Their inclusion remains a promising avenue for future research.

Challenges also arose during the preprocessing stage. The video dataset varied in quality, length, and resolution, and often included more than one person in the frame. This led to difficulties in keypoint extraction, as ViTPose sometimes captured keypoints from practitioners or other individuals rather than the patient. While we applied heuristics such as discarding frames with multiple detected persons, more advanced techniques such as person tracking and multi-view consistency checks would improve robustness. Standardizing the recording setup (e.g., fixed camera angles, consistent resolution, and removing background distractions) would also substantially improve data quality and downstream model performance.

5.2 Future Work

For future work, several directions can be pursued to improve both data quality and modeling approaches. First, the quality of the dataset should be systematically assessed, and appropriate measures should be taken to ensure consistency across recordings. In cases where manual editing or re-recording is not feasible, more advanced preprocessing techniques should be applied. For example, patient-specific object tracking, normalization of keypoints, and robust filtering strategies could be introduced to mitigate errors caused by multiple persons in the scene or variations in recording conditions.

Another critical limitation of this study is the class imbalance, particularly for the *FTLB* and *Both* categories. Expanding the dataset to include more examples of these underrepresented classes would significantly improve model performance and reduce bias toward the majority class (TS). Collaborations with other clinical centers could also facilitate the collection of larger and more balanced datasets, thereby enabling the use of more complex architectures.

From a methodological perspective, only ensemble models and temporal convolutional networks were fully implemented in this work due to time and resource constraints. In the future, transformer-based models and graph neural networks should be investigated, as initially proposed. With an increased dataset size, these architectures are expected to provide stronger performance, particularly graph neural networks, which are well-suited to spatio-temporal keypoint representations. Furthermore, the temporal convolutional networks used in this study could be revisited, with improved architectural design, systematic hyperparameter optimization, and stronger regularization to mitigate overfitting.

Finally, comprehensive ablation studies and interpretability analyses should be extended to multiple model families, including graph neural networks. This would allow for more robust identification of discriminative features across architectures. With larger datasets and richer analyses, such models have the potential to yield not only higher predictive accuracy but also clinically meaningful insights that can support differential diagnosis in practice.

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